

Terpenoid. Part VII. Synthesis of *trans*-(±)-Nuciferal*

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Based on the modified Wittig reaction of ethyl- α -diethylphosphonopropionate on 4-(*p*-tolyl)-*n*-valeraldehyde, the synthesis of *trans*-(±)-nuciferal has been achieved.

Nuciferal, a monocyclic aromatic sesquiterpene aldehyde, has been isolated[†] in dextro form from the volatile oil derived from the wood of *Torreya nucifera*. The structure (I) has been proposed for the aldehyde on the basis of spectral data and its relationship with α -curcumene for which the structure is well established².

The present investigation reports a synthesis of the title compound with the *trans*-geometry at the conjugated ethylenic bond. Nothing has been reported about the geometry of this double bond in the natural product.

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1. Sakai *et al.*, *Tetrahedron Letters*, 1963, No. 18, 1171.
2. Biroh and Mukherji, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1940, 2531.

The starting material, 4-(*p*-tolyl)-*n*-valeric acid³ (II) was converted *via* its acid chloride to 4-(*p*-tolyl)-*N*-methyl-*n*-valeramide (III) by treatment with *N*-methylaniline in pyridine solution in 86.5% yield. The latter, when reduced with lithium aluminium hydride⁴, furnished 4-(*p*-tolyl)-*n*-valeraldehyde (IV) in 44.4% yield. The aldehyde was characterised through its IR adsorption bands at 1720 and 2720 cm^{-1} . This aldehyde furnished yellow 2,4-DNP, m.p. 94° (lit.⁵, m.p. 94–95°).

The aldehyde (IV) was submitted to the modified Wittig reaction⁶ with ethyl α -diethylphosphonopropionate in presence of sodium hydride, using diethylglycol dimethyl ether as solvent, when ethyl 2-methyl-6-(*p*-tolyl)-*trans*-2-heptencarboxylate (V) was obtained in 72.8% yield. It has been reported that the Wittig reaction with an electron-acceptor group at the ylid-carbon of the phosphorylide molecule tends to be stereospecific, yielding only *trans*-isomer, which has been explained on the basis of electronic density distribution and less steric interaction of substituents in the transition state⁷. The formation of the *trans*-product (V) is further supported by the work of Wadsworth *et al.*⁸ who reported that only *trans*-olefins were formed by the action of phosphonate carbanion in modified Wittig reaction with aldehydes. Large number of olefins, using different aldehydes and phosphonate reagents, were prepared and studies in gas-liquid chromatography and nuclear magnetic resonance for *cis* and *trans* isomers in the olefins showed that only *trans*-olefins were formed.

The unsaturated ester (V) was reduced with LiAlH_4 when 2-methyl-6-(*p*-tolyl)-*trans*-2-hepten-1-ol (VI) was obtained in 80% yield. Its characteristic absorption peaks⁹ in IR and UV spectra are comparable with the naturally occurring nuciferol. The IR spectrum showed characteristic peaks at 3350, 1518, and 818 cm^{-1} (lit.¹ 3340, 1518, and 819 cm^{-1}). The UV spectrum showed peaks at 255, 265 and 275 $\text{m}\mu$ ($\log \epsilon$, 2.11, 2.60, and 2.75) [lit.¹ 252.5, 259, 264.5, 273, and 276.5 $\text{m}\mu$ ($\log \epsilon$, 2.57, 2.58, 2.75, 2.79, and 2.75)].

The allylic carbinol (VI) was smoothly oxidised with active manganese dioxide⁹ to 2-methyl-6-(*p*-tolyl)-*trans*-2-heptenal (I). The identity of the synthetic product (I) with the natural compound was established through comparison with IR and UV spectra. The

3. Rupe and Steinbach, *Ber.*, 1911, **44**, 595.

4. Nigam and Weedon, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1950, 4049.

5. Carter *et al.*, *ibid.*, 1939, 1504.

6. Wadsworth and Emmons, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1961, **83**, 1733.

7. Bergelson and Shemyakin, *Tetrahedron*, 1963, **19**, 149.

8. Wadsworth *et al.*, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1965, **30**, 680.

9. Attanburrow *et al.*, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1952, 1094; Mancera *et al.*, *ibid.*, 1953, 2189.

IR spectrum showed characteristic peaks at 2720, 1690, 1650, 1520, and 818 cm^{-1} [lit.¹ 2720, 1690, 1645, 1518, and 818 cm^{-1}]. The UV spectra showed peaks at 222, 229, 265, and 275 $\text{m}\mu$ ($\log \epsilon$, 4.17, 4.14, 2.93, and 2.90) [lit.¹ 222.5, 229, 264.5, 266.5, 273, and 279.5 ($\log \epsilon$, 4.19, 4.17, 2.97, 2.94, 2.96 and 2.50)].

The 2,4-DNP of (I) was prepared by the sulphuric acid method and crystallised from ethanol, m.p. 124° (lit. records m.p. 139-40°, due to dextro form).

EXPERIMENTAL*

4-(*p*-Tolyl)-*n*-valeric acid (II) was prepared according to the procedure laid down in the literature².

4-(*p*-Tolyl)-*N*-methyl-*n*-valeranimide (III).—To a solution of the acid (II) (6.0 g.) in dry benzene (50 ml) was slowly added thionyl chloride (7 g.). The contents were heated under reflux until the evolution of HCl had ceased and then evaporated. Distillation of the residue furnished the acid chloride (5 g., 76.9%), b.p. 120-25°/5 mm.

A solution of methylaniline (3 g.) in an equal volume of pyridine was slowly added to the acid chloride (5 g.) in benzene (45 ml), cooled in an ice bath. The mixture was shaken occasionally and kept at 20° for $\frac{1}{2}$ hr. Benzene extract was thoroughly washed with 2*N*-HCl and then with water. It was dried (Na_2SO_4) and evaporated. Distillation of the residue provided the methylanilide (III) (5.8 g., 86.5%), b.p. 215-18°/4 mm, n_D^{20} 1.5500. (Found: C, 81.00; H, 8.20; N, 5.00. Calc. for $\text{C}_{19}\text{H}_{23}\text{ON}$: C, 81.10; H, 8.24; N, 4.98%).

4-(*p*-Tolyl)-*n*-valeraldehyde (IV).—A solution of LiAlH_4 (230 mg.) in water (40 ml) was added slowly to a cooled and well-stirred solution of the methylanilide (III) (3 g.) in ether (10-15 ml). After the mixture had been stirred at 0° for 2 hr., a small volume of ethyl acetate was added (to decompose the excess of hydride), followed by 2*N*-HCl. The product was extracted with ether and the extract was washed thoroughly with 2*N*-HCl and then with water; it was dried (Na_2SO_4) and evaporated. The residue on distillation under reduced pressure provided 0.8 g. (44.4%), b.p. 130-34°/7 mm, n_D^{20} 1.5185. (Found: C, 81.60; H, 9.10. Calc. for $\text{C}_{12}\text{H}_{16}\text{O}$: C, 81.77; H, 9.15%).

The aldehyde afforded a yellow 2,4-DNP which after crystallisation from light petroleum melted at 94°. (Found: N, 15.9. Calc. for $\text{C}_{18}\text{H}_{20}\text{O}_4\text{N}_4$: N, 15.7%).

Ethyl 2-Methyl-6(*p*-tolyl)-trans-2-hepten-carboxylate (VI).—Sodium hydride (800 mg.) was placed in diethyl glycol dimethyl ether (35 ml). Ethyl α -diethylphosphonopropionate (3.70 g.) was added dropwise below 20° with stirring and the solution was stirred until the gas evolution had ceased. To the resultant yellow solution was then added aldehyde (IV) (2.7 g.) slowly below 25°. After the addition, the solution was further stirred for 1 hr. and then refluxed for $\frac{1}{2}$ hr. The product was extracted with ether after decomposing with a large excess of water, dried (Na_2SO_4), and evaporated. The residue

*The melting points and boiling points are uncorrected. Microanalyses by Mr. B. N. Anand, Microanalyst, Panjab University, Chemistry Department, Chandigarh. IR spectra were recorded on a Beckman I. R. 5 with sodium chloride optics using a thin liquid film and UV spectra on a Beckman model using 1 cm cell.

furnished on distillation $\alpha\beta$ -unsaturated ester (VI) (2.9 g., 72.8%), b.p. 156-62°/4mm, n_D^{16} 1.5020. (Found: C, 78.00; H, 9.59. Calc. for $C_{17}H_{24}O_2$: C, 78.42; H, 9.29%). IR absorption spectrum showed characteristic peaks at 1720 (conj. ester), 1635 cm^{-1} (conj. C=C).

2-Methyl-6-(p-tolyl)-trans-2-hepten-1-ol (VI).—To a suspension of $LiAlH_4$ (0.22 g.) in ether (30 ml) was added slowly and with stirring the $\alpha\beta$ -unsaturated ester (V) (3 g.) in ether (20 ml) at such a rate as to keep the ether at gentle reflux. After the mixture had been stirred for another 2 hr., a small volume of ethyl acetate was added, followed by a saturated solution of sodium sulphate. The product was extracted with ether, washed with water, dried (Na_2SO_4), evaporated, and distilled under reduced pressure to provide (VI) (2.7 g., 80%), b.p. 145-50°/4 mm, n_D^{18} 1.5060. (Found: C, 82.40; H, 10.05. Calc. for $C_{15}H_{22}O$: C, 82.51; H, 10.16%).

2-Methyl-6-(p-tolyl)-trans-2-hepten-1-al (I).—A mixture of the above alcohol (VI) (1g.) and active manganese dioxide (5 g.) in light petroleum (30 ml) was stirred at the room temperature for 2 hr. The mixture on filtration, evaporation, and on distillation under vacuum furnished (I) (0.8 g., 79.3%), n_D^{18} 1.5135. (Found: C, 83.00; H, 9.40. Calc. for $C_{15}H_{20}O$: C, 83.28; H, 9.32%).

The compound (I) afforded a deep red 2,4-DNP which after crystallisation from ethanol melted at 124°. (Found: N, 14.00. Calc. for $C_{21}H_{24}O_4N_4$: N, 14.13%).